

PEDAGOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES FOR DEVELOPING CREATIVITY IN
FUTURE TEACHERS ON THE BASIS OF ACCOLOGICAL APPROACH

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Annotation : *the axiological approach is a set of theoretical ideas focused on the system of socio-pedagogical values, the core of which is the understanding and affirmation of the value of human life, free creative activity and human communication.*

Key words: *the main goal of this approach is to assimilate the spiritual and material values of universal culture.*

In philosophical dictionaries, axiology is defined as the science of values. more description in the "pedagogical dictionary" gm kadjaspirova (m. 2000): axiology - is the material, cultural, spiritual, moral and psychological values of the individual, community, society, their relationship to the world of reality, values and values. a philosophical doctrine of changes in the system. historical development process.

ethical education tasks are traditional for the school, but today it is not about organizing students 'mastery of a system of values recognized by all members of the " adult " community, but about organizing the selection of a wide range of values. values of modern civilization (religious, ethnic-cultural, regional, national, state, etc.). d.). the essence of the value-axiological approach today is determined primarily by the situation of the assessment of what is happening (ideological, political, moral, aesthetic, etc.), in which man constantly determines his attitude to the world. And himself. The system of individual values is formed by introducing an individual to culture. In the process of acquiring culture (material and spiritual), a person becomes a person. Culture is "the highest level of spirituality and humanization, the improvement of the natural and social conditions of life and human relations, assimilated by the living and passed on to future generations." it

is a phenomenon of the human spirit, the inner essence of human ideas, the symbolically determined activity of people illuminated by humane and moral goals. Literature is a part of spiritual culture, and acquaintance with the art of speech becomes an important stage in the formation of the value sphere of an individual's personality, especially in the school years. Summarizing many definitions of values given in the scientific literature, we can say that the values are the formative units of the individual's consciousness, which determine the spheres of human life: the world, other people, a constant attitude towards himself. This set of relationships essentially shapes an individual's moral position, which is especially strong when it is conscious, when personal values emerge, when consciousness is seen as a general semantic formation.

This approach is based on a philosophical theory of values that emerged in the second half of the 19th century and as an independent scientific science in the 20th century. The theory of values has been widely used in various fields of scientific thought, including pedagogy, in particular, in the theory of education (vakarakovsky, ibkotova, vvkraevsky, etc.).

The meaning of the axiological approach can be explained through a system of axiological principles, which include:

- equality of philosophical views within a single humanistic system of values, while preserving the diversity of cultural and ethnic characteristics;

Equality of traditions and creativity, the need to study and apply the teachings of the past and the recognition of the possibilities of spiritual discoveries today and in the future, the mutual enrichment between traditionalists and innovators;

- socio-cultural pragmatism instead of demagogic arguments about the existential equality of people, the foundations of values, dialogue and asceticism instead of messianism and indifference.

According to this methodology, one of the primary tasks is to determine the human nature of science, including pedagogy, its relationship to the individual as a subject of knowledge, communication and creativity. This leads to the consideration of the values of philosophical and pedagogical knowledge, its "human aspect", its principles, and through them the humane, human nature of the whole culture. It is the humanistic direction of the philosophy of education that lays a solid foundation for the future of mankind.

The so-called groups of pedagogical values form an axiological model, in which values-goals define values-means, and values-relationships depend on values-goals and values-qualities, ie. they act as a unit. The axiological richness of the teacher determines the effectiveness and expediency of the selection and enhancement of new values, their behavioral motives, and the transition to

pedagogical action. Looking for ways to achieve the goals of pedagogical activity, the teacher chooses his professional strategy, the content of which is to develop himself and others. Consequently, the values and goals reflect the state education policy and the level of development of the science of pedagogy itself. Values are formed as a result of mastering the theory, methodology and pedagogical technologies, form the basis of a teacher's professional education. There are individual, group and social pedagogical values.

axiological approach is also of great importance. In scientific knowledge, it is extremely important that the universe, its object ,

event, phenomenon, etc., is reflected in the human mind, to determine the laws, degrees and possibilities of realization of values, its norms and criteria.

It relies on general cognitive theory (gnoseology)

as well as data from the social and natural sciences, especially the physiology of the higher nervous system, the evidence of sensory organs and mental activity , and the achievements of sciences such as logic and linguistics.

Understanding of values, the harmony of emotional and mental cognition in learning, the generalization of judgments ,

conclusions, concepts, terms and symbols, the analysis of axiological processes in natural and social reality, the practical activity based on them are interrelated organic processes.

and processes in the socio-sociological approach to life events

the importance of continuity, which is an expression of the interdependence, the historical connection, the cause and effect relationship, increases.

Such an approach has good scientific and practical results when applied to values and the processes associated with them .

In this case, values are manifested not as social phenomena that appear randomly and are not connected with each other, but as axiological systems and their elements, which in one period or another, social subjects are connected with others. Such an approach to values is based on the achievements of the social sciences, history, ethnography, demography and sociological research.

But the study of values is limited to just that

useless Perhaps reality , the forms of its manifestation, the value of events, phenomena and

processes, the understanding of their social significance are also extremely important. It is important to understand the social functions of these, their specific external influences. Only on the basis of an axiological approach it is possible to obtain correct information about the essence of values as a scientific category, their

differences from other concepts, objective bases and subjective perception, forms of manifestation . The activity is considered in terms of dignity and appreciation .

In this view, the value of value is not the utility, value and economic value that expresses them, but the value of value. 'p occurs. The study of this aspect of the matter is based on the arguments of ethics, aesthetics ,

jurisprudence, cultural studies, political science, and the social aspects of spirituality. In particular, the importance of economic, political, spiritual activities and processes for society and social actors, the problems that reflect different aspects of life and the views, ideas, doctrines, demands and needs that represent their solutions to real processes. is of great importance.

Hence, in the study of the universe and in the description of the laws of reality

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